

Cooperative Trajectory and Launch Power Optimization of UAV Deployed in Cross-Platform Battlefields

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Abstract: Trajectory planning is a complex problem, which involves meeting the physical constraints of the Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), constraints from the operating environment and other operational requirements. The foremost constraint to be met is that the paths must hold trim-set to maintain a stable flight whether exhibit solo or cluster pattern. Flyable paths are those that meet the kinematic constraints of the UAV. Satisfying this constraint ensures that the motion of the UAV stays within the maximum bounds on maneuver curvature. The safety of the path is measured by the ability of the path to avoid threats, obstacles and other UAVs. The path must maintain collision avoidance with other friendly UAVs and also must be flexible enough to avoid environmental obstacles and threats. The high-altitude multi-rotor, large-wheelbase UAV has better loading capacity, wind resistance, and endurance, its application in battlefields can fully reflect its value. The stability control of multi-rotor drones during high-altitude flight is a widely studied issue. First, combining the high-altitude multi-rotor dynamics model and the simulation modeling method of the multi-rotor UAV under the high-altitude flying wind field environment, the multi-rotor UAV semi-physical simulation platform is constructed and optimized. Secondly, a centralized clustering optimization algorithm CC-HVNA under the heterogeneous air-ground cooperative architecture is designed to implement clustering and coordinate message delivery through the cooperative control of roadside units and base stations. UAV data is uploaded based on network connectivity, and the infrastructure uses the collected UAV information to assist in clustering. Based on the modified K-means algorithm and cluster head election based on relative movement metrics, scale-constrained cluster generation is implemented. The cluster table is maintained to update the cluster. The control center implements message forwarding and scheduling by integrating the clustering information of the roadside unit and the base station. The proposed algorithm can effectively offload the base station load, reduce the control overhead of the clustering algorithm, and improve the delivery performance of security messages. Finally, the interactive simulation platform is used to simulate the implementation and comparative analysis of the algorithm proposed in this paper. The simulation results show that the collaborative optimization algorithm proposed in this paper can effectively improve the delivery performance of security messages and offload the load of cellular macro base stations, which will help Design a more optimized system architecture for future high-altitude multi-rotor drones.

Keywords: Unmanned Aerial Vehicle; Joint Optimization; Clustering Optimization Algorithm; Cross-platform Communication.

1. Introduction

The widespread availability and use of low-cost small multi-rotor UA, has enabled researchers and citizen scientists to explore the three dimensional world in ways that only a few decades ago would have seemed impossible. Experiments in aerial photography, mapping and mineral exploration, environmental monitoring and disaster recovery from earthquakes, Tsunami, landslides and nuclear accidents, have all become a reality thanks to these type of systems. In developing the next generation of unmanned systems, such as the tethered small multi-rotor capable of persistent surveillance, developers will need to convince governmental agencies, like the Civil Aviation Authority, as well as the average citizen, of the benefits, safety and security of such systems, when used appropriately. High-altitude multi-rotor unmanned aerial vehicle (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle), that is, an unmanned aircraft, refers to an aircraft that includes navigation and positioning systems, flight control computers, and other avionics equipment. It can use radio remote control or on-board programs for semi-automatic or autonomous flight. Research on drones has begun, and these studies were first applied in the military field. In recent years, with the reduction of the size of a series of sensors and processing chips, such as inertial measurement units, and technological advancement, micro-unmanned aerial vehicles have gradually appeared in people's field of vision [1-3].

An algorithm was designed to find the shortest route in flight space using visual navigation information, not only taking into account the kinematics and dynamics of UAV, but also introducing and evaluating its navigation capabilities; the algorithm uses landmark visual navigation with limited GPS information. The real-time status update is achieved by matching the aerial camera with the built-in map [4]. Observe natural landmarks with a single embedded camera, and provide visual navigation for UAVs that take off and land vertically [5]. AR. Drone UAV is used as the platform, and SLAM technology combined with monocular vision and inertial navigation is used to implement the fuzzy logic controller [6]. Starting from the camera imaging model, the aircraft state is estimated according to the image information, so as to obtain the required navigation

parameters to achieve tracking of the target. In the target detection, it is assumed that the target has obvious features or sufficient prior knowledge to make the detection. The tasks of the phase are greatly simplified [7]. Due to the unpredictability of the real wind field and the use of wind tunnel tests for small unmanned aerial vehicles such as quadrotors, the cost is relatively high compared to the engineering design process. Therefore, most of the researches on the wind resistance of multirotor drones are also. The method of modeling and analysis is completed by simulation [8,9]. The additional speed generated by the vortex ring and the induced speed calculated by the momentum theory are superimposed. The closer the vortex ring is to the paddle, the greater the additional speed, which introduces some non-linear characteristics [10,11] which can show the aircraft in real-time simulation. Uncontrolled drop and "power sink" phenomenon. However, this type of simulation model only uses the semi-empirical shape function to estimate the average flow characteristics of the rotor flow field in the vortex ring state in the vortex ring state region, and cannot reflect the fluctuation characteristics of the helicopter rotor tension and torque in the vortex ring state in real time [12-14], this is also the main flaw of the VRS model. The user data rate is used as the evaluation index [15-17]. The goal is to find the optimal deployment location of the UAV base station, and meet the user's downlink data rate requirements with the minimum transmission power. Considering that the base station uses frequency division multiple access technology, there is a trade-off between the number of users in the cell and the transmission power of the base station. The algorithm obtains the optimal solution through iteration. Each iteration includes two steps [18-20]. First, find the optimal position of the drone base station given the coverage of the drone base station. This corresponds to the general ground base station selection. Address problem; then adjust the drone coverage to reduce the total transmission power of the drone base station under a given deployment location, that is, determine the association between the user and the base station, which can be solved with the help of optimal transmission theory. Before the emergence of the multi-rotor drone, the research on the wind resistance characteristics of the rotorcraft was completed on the object of a manned helicopter.

The wind tunnel test was used to evaluate the helicopter's suspension in any direction and different wind field strength the most direct way is to change the stability of the stop and the attitude of the trim.

In summary, In order to analyze the key technologies of air-ground collaborative optimization of high-altitude multi-rotor UAV, the main components of atmospheric motion and mathematical models of wind field are introduced first. The main components of atmospheric motion and mathematical models of wind field are introduced first. Next, a model-based assessment method for wind resistance rating of a high altitude multi-rotor unmanned aerial vehicle is introduced, and the accuracy of the assessment method is verified in combination with experimental data. Aiming at the stability of the control law in the disturbance of the wind field, the linearization tools provided by Matlab were used to obtain the transfer function of the disturbance channel of the aircraft under the open and closed loop control laws. The hover control law was analyzed and demonstrated. Secondly, a centralized clustering scheme CC-HVNA is proposed under the air-ground cooperative architecture of high-altitude multi-rotor UAV. Firstly, the component functions in the architecture and the state transition under centralized clustering are analyzed, and the cluster admission detection mechanism used in clustering and the drone information uploading mechanism based on network connectivity are introduced, and then a modification based on K-means is proposed Cluster partitioning and cluster maintenance methods based on clustered tables, and finally designed a data distribution scheme for content under centralized clustering.

2. Coordinated position of high-altitude multi-rotor drone

2.1 High-altitude multi-rotor drone position

In the process of designing a high-altitude multi-rotor drone, the wind resistance level is a relatively important design indicator, so the model should be combined and the corresponding experimental data should be used to evaluate its wind resistance. It is mainly about unmanned Appearance of different

aircraft strengths to maintain the controllability of a fixed attitude and position.

High-altitude multi-rotor UAV real-time acquisition of its own position information is an important basis for its autonomous flight and a key component of the UAV control system. Due to some body's own reasons and environmental limitations, GPS and lidar-based navigation technology has no room for development. In this case, how to accurately and quickly estimate the position information of the drone becomes particularly important. In the recognition of air-ground targets, drones rely on the downward-facing camera to obtain the target position and target movement. In order to expand the field of view, a fisheye lens is added in front of the camera to obtain scene information with a larger angle of view. The pre-processing of visual images and the accurate recognition of targets are the key to UAV tracking targets and completing air-ground collaborative tasks. The air-ground cooperative information distribution application system is shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Air-ground cooperative information distribution of high-altitude multi-rotor drone.

Assume that the UAV performs a information distribution task within a certain fixed height H over the combat area and performs a limited time T.

The set $N = \{1, 2, \dots, n, \dots, N\}$ represents the ground combat unit deployed in the combat area. In general, the safe launch and landing areas of drones are known to be represented by (x_0, y_0, H) and (x_f, y_f, H) , and (x_0, y_0, H) can be used as the

origin of coordinates. Under the condition of time requirements, the total time T can be divided into M hour slots, and the length of each time slot is δ , that is, $T = M\delta$. Among them, with the increase of the number of time slots M taken and the decrease of the time slot length, not only will it increase more optimization variables and calculation complexity, but it will also provide a more accurate approximate flight trajectory. So the drone's flight trajectory can be approximated as: $\{x[m], y[m], H\}, m \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$.

Considering the limitation of the maximum flying speed V of the drone, the position of the drone should be subject to the following restrictions:

$$\begin{cases} [x(1) - x_0]^2 + [y(1) - y_0]^2 \leq (V\delta)^2 \\ [x(m) - x(m-1)]^2 + [y(m) - y(m-1)]^2 \leq (V\delta)^2 \\ [x_f - x(m)]^2 + [y_f - y(m)]^2 \leq (V\delta)^2 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Considering the energy constraints required for high-altitude multi-rotor drone flight, the dynamic power of the drone during flight will be restricted. According to [21], the relationship between the power $P_f(V)$ and the speed V of the drone when flying:

$$P_f(V) = P_o \left(1 + \frac{3V^2}{U_p^2}\right) + P_t \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{V^4}{4v_0^4} - \frac{V^2}{2v_0^2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} d_0 \rho s A V^3 \quad (2)$$

Since the above-mentioned UAV flight height H is fixed, the analysis focuses on $\{x(m), y(m)\}$ after the dimensionality reduction process. The information distribution mode uses orthogonal frequency division multiple access, and the total bandwidth and transmission power are represented by B and P_f , respectively, while equal bandwidth is allocated to each ground communication node. According to reference [22], the channel power gain of the drone and the n -th node at the m -th slot is controlled by line-of-sight.

$$g_n(m) = \frac{\beta_0}{[x(m) - x_n]^2 + [y(m) - y_n]^2 + H^2} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Air density and wind resistance level of high-altitude multi-rotor drone

As shown in Figure 2, the corresponding wind-attitude curve that can be fitted is calculated using the balancing work points of the corresponding attitude angles under different wind speeds. The horizontal axis in Figure 2 represents the strength of the wind, and the vertical axis represents the corresponding Under the strength of the wind field, the trimmed wind-resistant attitude angle formed by the drone in order to maintain the position of the single channel combines the effectiveness of the model and the speed required for the drone to fly. When designing the control rate, the drone should be designed The set value corresponding to the maximum attitude angle of the aircraft is limited to 30 degrees, and the corresponding wind resistance is greater than 20 meters per second, which achieves a unique coverage of the fifth-level wind strength range.

Fig.2. Corresponding wind-attitude curve.

Investigate the impact of air density on the motor blade model. As shown in Table 1, we can calculate 50% of the PWM setting value (that is, the value 1500) to control the motor to drive the blade to rotate according to the established motor blade model. Lift at different altitudes. As shown in Table 1, as the altitude increases, the air density decreases, and the lift generated by the rotor will also decrease at the same speed.

Table 1
Lift provided by multi-rotor at different altitudes with 50% PWM output

Altitude (m)	Air density (kg/m ³)	Rotor lift (N), 50% PWM operating point
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10	1.299	12.61
1000	1.271	11.54
1500	1.214	11.04
2000	1.16	9.67
3000	0.9674	8.76
4000	0.873	7.87
5000	0.765	6.89

During the design of the control law of the high-altitude multi-rotor UAV, the outputs of the four control channels of throttle, roll, pitch, and yaw are mapped to the PWM wave outputs of the eight motors correspondingly controlled through a certain linear relationship. Therefore, if the control channel output changes a fixed value, the PWM wave will also change the fixed value in a certain proportion.

In the model, the altitude is used as a single variable, and the typical working altitudes are 10m (Hangzhou area), 1200m (Northwest field altitude), 2200m (Northwest flight apex), 3200m, 4200m. At each altitude, the PWM increases from a value of 1500 to a maximum of 2000 at denser intervals, and the corresponding motor lift is recorded, and a PWM-lift curve diagram of a single rotor operating at different altitudes can be obtained.

Fig.3. PWM-Lift Curves of Rotating Ji at Different Altitude Positions.

As shown in Figure. 3, as the altitude increases, the maximum lift output value of the rotor PWM-lift curve is compressed, and at the same time, the corresponding curve slope gradually decreases at the position where the lift output is 13.8N. From the above curve, we can calculate the lift change corresponding to the 50% increase or decrease of the PWM value (that is, a 5% change of a single control channel) at the lift operating point position.

Table 2.

Lift changes due to fixed control channels of multi-rotor

operating points at different altitudes

Altitude (m)	Air density (kg/m ³)	Single motor provides 13.8N corresponding speed PWM	Increase / decrease of 50 by PWM (5% change in control channel) to generate rotor lift change (N)	
10	1.279	1568	+1.79	-1.77
1200	1.158	1542	+1.62	-1.57
1700	1.192	1602	+1.54	-1.5
2200	1.139	1613	+1.65	-1.44
4000	0.7626	1712	+1.12	-1.17

As shown in Table 2, maintaining the same set of control parameters, when flying in high altitude areas, the change in single rotor pull produced by the same control channel increment is smaller than that in low altitude areas. In the case of the inertia of the drone and the relative position of a single motor to the center of mass of the body unchanged, the steering torque generated by the output of the same control channel will also be reduced, that is, the output of the entire object system from the control channel to the angular rate of the drone. The open-loop gain changes. It can be concluded from this that the change in air density caused by changes in altitude will directly shift the position of the linear operating point of the system.

3. Air-ground cooperative communication distribution optimization of multi-rotor UAV

3.1 Collaborative distribution optimization based on centralized clustering

1) Clustering scale: When the clustering scale is too small, there may be more nodes. In addition, the reduction of the cluster size will lead to an increase in the number of clusters in the system, which will lead to stronger inter-cluster interference. The maximum number of accesses determined by the processing capacity of the cluster head and limited wireless resources limit the size of the clustering. Otherwise, the performance of the communication message delivery within the cluster will deteriorate. Therefore, the algorithm is considered to preset the clustering size based on empirical values.

2) Clustering radius: Generally speaking, the cluster radius is determined by the communication range of the nodes. In the algorithm, the clustering radius is set smaller than the communication range of the nodes and a clustering threshold value slightly larger than the clustering radius is given. Reliable communication can be performed between

the cluster head and the cluster members within the communication range corresponding to the clustering threshold.

3) Cluster members: Subject to the air-ground topology and traffic regulations, the same-direction drones in the actual vehicle environment often have similar behavior patterns, and it is easy to generate more stable clusters. Therefore, only the same-direction drones can be clustered in the algorithm.

We use K-means algorithm to perform cluster division. According to the previous stage of UAV information collection, centralized cluster division is performed periodically in base stations and roadside units. If no drone messages were collected in the previous cycle, the base station and roadside unit will wait for the next clustering. Let N_c, S_v, S_p denote the number of clusters, the set of co-directional drones, and the preset cluster size, respectively. Then the initial cluster number satisfies:

$$N_c = \frac{Size(S_v)}{S_p} \quad (4)$$

The pseudo code of the cluster division and cluster head selection process is shown in Table 3. First, the standard K-means clustering needs to be performed based on the drone position information extracted from the drone set S_v . Next, the cluster head election needs to be performed in each cluster. To this end, a weighted metric FitFactor is defined, which describes the priority of the node to become the cluster head. The smaller the value, the higher the priority of the node and the cluster head survival time. The longer the cluster, the better the stability of the cluster can be expressed as:

$$FitFactor = c_D \times |D_{nom}| + c_v \times |V_{nom}| \quad (5)$$

$$c_D + c_v = 1$$

Table 3

Cluster division and cluster head selection process

Cluster division and cluster head selection	
Input:	Number of clusters N_c ;
	S_v : Drone collection;
	R_p : Preset clustering radius;
Output:	S_c : Clustered collection;
1: LOOP:	
2:	$S_c \leftarrow Kmeans(S_v, N_c)$;
3:	For each Cluster. in S_c Do
4:	For each Vehicles in Cluster. Do

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5:   FitFactor =  $c_D \times |D_{nom}| + c_v \times |V_{nom}|$ 
6:   End for
7:    $CH_i \leftarrow$  The vehicle with the minimum
      FitFactor;
For each Vehicles in Cluster. Do
  If  $\exists Distance(Vehicle, CH_i) > R_p$  Then
     $N_c = N_c + 1$ 
     $S_c = \emptyset$ 
    Goto Loop;
  End if
End for
End for
    
```

Among them, D_{nom} represents the normalized distance between the drone and the cluster center, V_{nom} represents the normalized speed of the drone, and c_D, c_v represents the weight of distance and speed in the cluster head election. . In particular, when $c_D = 0$, the algorithm will select the drone whose speed is closest to the average speed of the cluster as the cluster head; when $c_v = 0$, the algorithm will select the drone that is closer to the cluster center as the cluster head. Considering the constraints of the preset clustering radius, we need to test the divided clusters. If the distance between the elected cluster head and the cluster members is greater than the preset clustering radius, increase the number of clusters N_c by 1, and repeat Global clustering process. The above clustering process will continue until the divided clusters meet a preset clustering radius limit.

3.2 Air-ground cooperative dynamic optimization of UAV base stations based on Markov approximation

The control station in the system is used for the assignment of the UAV base station and the initialization of the base station parameters. Firstly, the optimal deployment height h of the UAV base station under a given Qos, such as the received signal strength, is determined from the empirical data according to the task environment, and this height corresponds to the maximum coverage of the UAV base station. Next, the task area A is divided. Considering that the task area is rectangular, the area can be divided into

$ceil(\frac{length(A)}{z}) \times ceil(\frac{width(A)}{z})$. Where Z is the preset side length of the grid, and its value can be determined by the coverage radius r of the drone base station. Considering that the drone base station can completely cover the grid area, the side length can be set to $z = \sqrt{2}r$. The circle corresponding to the coverage area of the base station is the circumscribed circle of the grid. The control station will assign a unique id to each drone base station and arbitrarily select a set of initial configuration for each drone base station, that is, $f^0 = \{(c_n^0, p_n^0) | n \in N\}$, where the initial position allocation must ensure that there is no overlap between positions, and the position number needs As the drone id increases. After obtaining the id, initial channel-position configuration, position number-position mapping, state transition parameters, and position transition matrix, the UAV base station is deployed to the initial position according to the parameter configuration.

Table 4
Generation of transferable state sets

Get transferable location collection
Input: S: position shift matrix; L: number of horizontal grids; p^f : Configure the set of drone base station deployment locations under f;
Output: $p_n^{f,f}$ UAV base station n transferable location set;
1: Initialization: $p_n^{f,f} = \emptyset$;
2: Extract $p_n^f = (l_n^f, w_n^f)$ from p^f ;
3: Calculate the index $i = (l_n^f - 1) * L + w_n^f$;
4: For each S_{ij} . Do
5: If $S_{ij} = 1$ Then
$p = \lfloor j / L + 1 \rfloor$
Add p to $p_n^{f,f}$;
End if
End for
Return $p_n^{f,f}$

In order to achieve initialization synchronization, a timer can be set according to the farthest deployment location of the drone base station. When the timer expires, that is, when the last drone base station completes deployment, the initialization phase ends.

4. Experimental verification

The simulation area contains 1 base station and 4 roadside units. Each section has two-way roads. At the start of the simulation, all drones are randomly deployed in the scene and set off at a random speed. In order to study the impact of traffic density, cluster size, and CAM data volume on message delivery, we changed the number of drones in the simulation, the maximum allowed cluster size, and the CAM service area. The detailed simulation parameters are given in Table 5.

To illustrate the effectiveness of the clustering scheme, we compare the other two schemes. One is 802.11 p-only. In this scheme, the roadside unit only acts as a relay node, and the drone will continue to forward messages until the drone outside the target delivery area receives the message. The other is LTE-only. In this mode, the source drone uploads the CAMS to the base station, and then the data is distributed by the base station to all drones in its coverage area. We use two metrics to evaluate the proposed scheme: packet delivery rate and end-to-end delay. In order to illustrate the effective support of the centralized clustering scheme for intersection collision avoidance applications, we evaluated the drone message delivery rate within the range of 0-1000m for CAM-related intersections. In addition, in order to illustrate the efficiency of the proposed data distribution scheme and the effective support of centralized clustering for traffic congestion warning applications, we compared the message delivery performance of different target delivery areas.

Table 5
Centralized clustering simulation parameter configuration

Parameter	Value
Simulation area size	35kmx35km
Simulation time	60s
Speed limit	60km/h
Number of drones	5-30
CAM service area	1000-3000m
CAM transmission interval	100s
Clustering radius	4000m
Maximum allowable cluster size	1-10
Drone communication range	5000m
Roadside unit communication range	7000m
Base station coverage	1.8km

In the first set of simulations, the CAM service range was set to 3000m, and the maximum allowed cluster size MACS was set to 10. Figure 4 shows the comparison of delivery performance when the

(a) Clustering ratio
(b) Member ratio

Fig.6. Clustering ratio and the proportion of members in the system when the size of different clusters is limited.

Figure 5 shows the packet delivery rate and end-to-end delay of different packet target delivery areas when the maximum allowed cluster size MACS changes under centralized clustering. With the increase of MACS, the packet delivery rate shows an upward trend, and the end-to-end delay shows a downward trend. This is because the increase of MACS reduces the number of clusters in the system, resulting in reduced inter-cluster interference. However, when the MACS reaches a certain value, two situations may occur. On the one hand, the cluster head is overloaded due to too many members in the access cluster; on the other hand, it can be seen from Figure 6 that with the increase of MACS, only a small number of clusters in the system can reach the MACS. With the creation of more small-scale clusters, the number of nodes that can directly communicate with base stations and roadside units will also fluctuate. The degree of fluctuation depends on the distribution of drones in the system, so the message delivery performance may occur larger. From this set of simulations, it can be seen that for single-hop cluster message delivery, appropriate cluster size limits are important to improve the performance of secure message delivery.

In the first simulation, we fixed the state transition parameter γ to 0.5, and adjusted the value of the optimization interval parameter β to observe the change in system throughput measurement, as shown in Figure 7 (a).

Fig.7. (a) Dynamic change of system throughput under different β values (b) Dynamic change of system throughput under different γ values.

As shown in Figure 7, as the value of β increases, the throughput when the system converges is closer to the optimal system throughput. When the value of β is 20, an optimization interval of 2.17% can be achieved. When the value of β is small, the countdown time of the drone base station is negligible compared with the throughput measurement interval and the time required for state transition. When β approaches infinity, although the optimization interval approaches 0, the countdown time will also increase accordingly. With the same convergence round, the system convergence time will be longer. In the simulation, we set the optimization interval parameter β to 20, and adjust the value of the state transition parameter γ . The average system throughput change is shown in Figure 7 (b). It can be clearly seen that the smaller

the γ value, the larger the initial average throughput measurement. This is because as the γ decreases, the drone base station is more inclined to choose to move to a new location in the state transition. UAV base stations can obtain larger system measurements, and the system converges faster. Because γ does not affect the convergence interval, the system throughput will converge to the same value when there are enough state transition rounds.

Considering that the time required for the system to fully converge is too long, in actual operation, the regional traffic distribution is not constant, so we examine the average system throughput corresponding to the drone base station when completing 100 state transitions and compare it with random state transitions. Compared with the scheme RST and the minimum throughput transfer scheme MTST, during this operating time, it can be approximately considered that the traffic in each area is stable or there are only small changes. We changed the values of the optimization interval parameter β and the state transition parameter γ to observe the average throughput of the system. Due to the randomness of the initial state, we performed 1000 simulations and gave a 95% confidence interval. The simulation results are shown in Figure 8.

Fig.8. (a) Comparison of system throughput under different β values ((b) Comparison of system throughput under different γ values.

Overall, the proposed algorithm is significantly better than the other two algorithms. Because the state transition under the RST and MTST schemes does not depend on β , its throughput changes fluctuate, and the increase in γ parameters will cause the average throughput under all schemes. In addition, although the mean value of the MTST scheme is greater than the RST scheme, the confidence interval under this scheme is wider. During the simulation process, it can be observed that the MTST scheme tends to transfer to limited states.

5. Conclusion

Based on the model and experimental data, this paper verifies the wind resistance level in the design requirements of the UAV and the robustness of the control law in the case of wind field disturbance. Regarding the vortex ring state, referring to the Gaussian criterion for the main rotor of the helicopter, a descent strategy of forward flight gliding was explored. The transmission power and trajectory optimization of a UAV-assisted network that provides unmanned aerial vehicles with network access to ground combat equipment wireless nodes are studied. Jointly optimize the trajectory and launch power of the UAV to maximize the minimum average throughput. In the battlefield application, the airspace UAV platform can realize the coverage and distribution of information on the ground single

soldier and the ground combat unit, and realize the cross-platform battlefield information. A centralized clustering scheme under heterogeneous vehicle-road collaboration architecture is proposed. This scheme implements clustering and coordinate message delivery through the cooperative control of roadside units and base stations. With the Markov approximation to the original problem, we construct a Markov chain. Through the implementation of the Markov chain, we design a distributed drone base station deployment algorithm based on throughput measurement and state transfer. The human-machine base station determines the deployment location and operating channel through the cooperation between each other, thereby effectively serving the hotspot area of data traffic and alleviating the data traffic pressure of the ground base station. UAV base station deployment algorithm only considers system throughput optimization indicators. Considering constraints such as user classification and business QoS classification, how to deploy UAV base stations to achieve multi-objective optimization remains to be studied.

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